

IN-MOULD COATING OF THERMOSETTING COMPOSITES WITH POLYSULFONE

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Keywords: Thermoplastic films, Thermoset composites, Manufacturing, Multi-functional properties, Mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

Recently, surface finish of composites and ease of processing have led to the extensive use of coating resins in the moulds prior to moulding. The types of coatings currently used include spray (using powder and liquid resins) or painting (using a liquid resins). The most important aspect of in-mould coating is to deposit a homogeneously even-thickness layer of material which is quite difficult to obtain by conventional mould coating methods. In this study, we manufactured thin PES film using a conventional laboratory extruder. We successfully demonstrated that the films can be used in the mould as coating material during the fabrication of carbon fibre reinforced thermosetting polymer (CFRP) panels due to its miscibility to the thermosetting resins. The resulting CFRP composites can be de-moulded easily and the PES film is therefore adhered to the composites after curing step leaving a smooth and shiny surface finish. In order to further exploit the PES used in this study, we also demonstrated that we can build interleave CFRP composites with PES films and the mechanical performance of various interleave designs will be presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Coatings of a composite material have been extensively used for many aesthetic structural parts such as automotive body panels or as a protection against ultraviolet (UV) light and decomposition under long exposure to UV rays. The most common type of coating is manual or automated painting of composite parts post-moulding. However this type of coating is both time consuming and expensive and hence new technologies are being sought to solve the problem associated with post-mould coating. One type of coating is application of liquid or dry-spray painting, which can be applied on the surface of the mould prior to curing or on the product after the curing but before de-moulding [1]. In this study, we embarked on a new method for in-mould coating by using a thermoplastic film material, polyethylene sulfone. We chose this material as the base material mainly because PES is miscible to epoxy and therefore it will create a good adhesion to the outer surface of the composite part moulded. PES is a transparent resin which has a high heat resistivity (T_g of 225 °C) and flame resistance.

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites have been used for many structural materials due to its lightweight, high strength and stiffness to weight ratio. However, in any laminated composites, delamination is known as the weakest failure mode when load is applied to such composites. There have been many methods studied to tackle the issues related to delamination in carbon fibre composites. Some methods include improving the toughness of the composites by modifying the constituents or by improving the fibre/matrix adhesion. Interleaving carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites is one of the easiest and vastly studied for increasing the toughness of the composites. Interleaf here means that the composite laminates are sandwiched between a thin layer of tough and ductile thermoplastic film [REF]. Aksoy et al. [2] studied the effect of thermoplastic and thermoset

interleaved graphite/epoxy composites. The authors concluded that thermoplastic interleaved composites improved the fracture toughness of the composite much better than a thermoset interleaved due to the combination of high strain to failure and yield strength of the thermoplastic films. Interleave composites are also designed for improving the impact strength and delamination resistance of CFRP [3]. By utilising PES features as an in-mould coating material, we also study the effect of PES interleaved unidirectional composites.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Materials

Polyethersulfone 5003P, a coating grade polymer was kindly supplied by Sumitomo Chemicals (Machelen, Belgium). Unidirectional carbon fibre epoxy, HEXPLY 914C was purchased from Hexcel (Duxford, Cambridge UK).

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Manufacturing of PES films

A laboratory scale 15 cc double screw micro compounder (DSM Xplore, Geleen, The Netherlands) was used to manufacture continuous PES nanocomposite films. Pure PES powder was fed through the feeder and at the top of the compounder and entered the vertical barrel by gravitational force. There are 3 heating zones on the barrel of the micro compounder. The temperature of the barrel were set to 290 °C, 310 °C and 330 °C from the feeder to the exit, respectively. The screw speed was set to 35 rpm throughout the process. A 35 mm (W) x 0.4 mm (H) cast film die was attached at the exit of the micro compounder, which serves as the mould. An air knife was used after the film die to minimize necking phenomena. Two-drum winders were used to wind and collect the manufactured films. The drum winder speed was set to 1 m/min.

2.2.2 PES as in-mould coating material

A steel mould having a cavity dimensions of 12 mm (W) x 10 mm (H) x 150 mm (L) was used in this study. Two PES films of 12 mm (W) x 0.1 mm (H) x 150 mm (L) was used as a mould coating material. One of the PES film was first laid down on the mould cavity. Ten layers of 0° fibre direction HexPly 914C (UD) prepregs of 12 mm (W) x 150 mm (L) was then laid on top of the PES film. To finish the layup, the other PES film was then placed on top of the composite prepregs. The top of the specimen was secured by a stainless steel plunger of 12 mm (W) x 10 mm (H) x 150 mm (L). The mould was then placed into a hydraulic press (Carver Inc., Indianan, USA). The press was heated at a heating rate of 5 °C to 175 °C and 7 bar pressure was applied. The curing time was set to 1 hour and the specimen was post-cured at 190 °C for 4 hours. The mould was then removed from the hot press and set to cool at ambient temperature.

2.2.3 Interleaved unidirectional (UD) composite preparation

Three interleaved composite laminate designs were manufactured along with control pure composite laminate. The designs are shown in Figure 1 termed as Design A, B and C. **Design A** consist of a total of 16 plies of 0° fibre direction CFRP (UD) and four PES film interleaved within the laminate. Each PES film was placed between four CFRP laminate (Figure 1). **Design B** consist of a total of 18 plies of 0° fibre direction CFRP (UD) sandwiched between two PES films on the top and bottom of the laminate. **Design C** has one PES film inserted in the midplane of the laminate. The laminate consists of 20 plies of CFRP 0° fibre direction (UD). Finally, pure CFRP laminate with 20 plies of 0° fibre direction CFRP (UD) was fabricated and used as control laminate. The schematic below shows the different designs with dark grey rectangles represents PES films within the composite laminate.

Figure 1. Schematic showing the different interleaved composite designs

The composite laminates were prepared in a steel mould having a cavity dimension of 12 mm (W) x 200 mm (L). The mould is equipped with a rectangular plunger to act as the top cover for the cavity. The interleaved laminates were placed in the mould and the plunger was placed on top of the specimen. The mould was then placed into a hot press and followed a curing cycle as detailed in section 2.2.2. The specimen for short beam shear test was cut using a diamond blade cutter to 20 mm long (Diadisc 4200, Mutronic GmbH, Rieden am Forggensee, Germany). The edges were trimmed using a scalpel blade to remove any excess burrs.

2.2.4 Short beam shear test

One of the simplest ways to characterise the effect of interleaved composite is through short beam shear test. This is mainly because the specimen size required to carry out the test is relatively small and the data is reliable as means of comparison on the effect of different interleaved designs. During the test, interlaminar shear is generated through a three-point-bending mode mainly because of the short span to thickness ratio. The laminates of 12 mm x 20 mm x 2 mm were secured into a 3 point bend test jig in an Instron equipped with 50 kN load cell (Model 4505, high Wycombe, Buckinghamshire, UK). The span to thickness ratio was set to 4.0 and the specimen was loaded at a crosshead speed of 1 m/min until failure according to ASTM D2344. The short beam shear strength, F^{sbs} was calculated as:

$$F^{sbs} = 0.75 \frac{P_m}{bd} \quad (1)$$

where P_m is the maximum load observed during the test, b and h are the measured specimen width and thickness, respectively. All measurements were repeated on at least 5 different samples per interleaved design to obtain a statistical significant average. The error bars presented are standard deviations from the average values.

2.2.5 Specimen preparation for microscopy study

The interleaved composites were first cut into 12 mm (W) x 10 mm (L) using a diamond blade cutter (Diadisc 4200, Mutronic GmbH, Rieden am Forggensee, Germany). The specimen was then embedded into a polishing epoxy media (EpokwickTM, Buehler, Lake Bluff, Illinois, USA) and left to cure over night at room temperature. The cured epoxy was then polished using a series of sandpaper and final polishing using 6 μ m, 3 μ m and 1 μ m diamond suspensions. The polished specimen was then viewed under the microscope (Carl Zeiss MicroImaging GmbH, Gottingen, Germany). Several images of the specimen were captured using a static camera (AxioCam ERc, Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 PES as in-mould coating material

PES is an amorphous thermoplastic that melts at 330 °C. Upon curing of the HexPly 914C at 175 °C and post-curing at 190 °C, the PES film that was used in the mould as the top and bottom layer was adhered neatly to the CFRP panel produced. The entire panel was removed from the mould easily without any prior application of mould release material. The surface of the CFRP panel with PES film was also shown to be shiny as compared to pure CFRP panel (Figure 2). Furthermore, there is no delamination occurring on the surface of the composite panel fabricated. This motivated us to study the use of PES film as interleaf layers in the UD composite and the effect of this PES material on the composites studied.

Figure 2. Unidirectional HexPly 914C upon curing in the mould (A) without PES film and (B) with PES film placed on the mould surface prior to moulding.

3.2 Effect of PES interleaved HexPly 914C composites on interlaminar shear properties

Short beam shear test is one of the simplest, quickest and used as a ranking tool or quality control test in industries. It has been used as a means to study the effect of interleaf on interlaminar properties of composite materials. The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of control HexPly 914C and interleaved design A, B and C is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Interlaminar shear strength of Control HexPly 914C and PES interleaved composites A, B and C

The ILSS of control HexPly 914C was measured to be 101 MPa. The ILSS of PES interleaved composite **A**, **B** and **C** was measured to be 74 MPa, 94 MPa and 105 MPa, respectively (Figure 3). The ILSS of PES interleaved composite in design A was reduced significantly by 27% as compared to control HexPly 914C. The load-displacement curves of all the composites are shown in figure 4. It can be seen that composite in design A failed at a lower load values, and at the same time, the load-displacement is showing of a more ductile-behaviour. This can only be associated to having four ductile thermoplastic layers of PES films in the composites and instead of failing at interlaminar shear, the composite failed under compression/tension failure. Design **A** has also the lowest numbers of unidirectional Hexply 914C as compared to design **B** and **C**.

Figure 4. Load-displacement of Hexply 914C control specimen and PES interleaved Design **A**, **B** and **C**

On the other hand, Design B and C failed with interlaminar shear failure similar to that of the control HexPly 914C. It is apparent that Design C gives the highest ILSS in all the composites tested. Having only one PES film in the centre of the laminates helped to improve the maximum load to failure of the composite. Furthermore, the load displacement curve of PES interleaved Design C shows that the failure mechanism of the composite is rather gradual and not as catastrophic as in the control HexPly 914C material. It is important to source an interleaved material that is compatible to the epoxy in the matrix. A poor adhesion between interleaved material/epoxy may lead to low ILSS properties [4]. The cross-section images from the microscope shows a very good compatibility between PES and epoxy in the interleaved composites (Figure 5). There are no clear distinction exist between the two polymers on the composite cross-section (Figure 5B). Therefore, it is suffice to say that the PES film used in this study is very compatible to the epoxy used thus PES can lead to the improvement in the ILSS of the interleaved composites.

Figure 5. Cross-section images of (A) Control HexPly 914C and (B) PES interleaved HexPly 914C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we have shown that an amorphous thermoplastic PES film can be used as an in-mould coating material for the fabrication of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. The adhesion between the PES film and the epoxy composites is excellent as there are no distinct interface was formed after the composite was cured. We further investigated the impact of PES interleaved carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. Three interleaved composite designs were fabricated and the ILSS properties were characterised. It shows that having only one PES film interleaved in the midplane of the composite enhances the ILSS of the composite compared to control composites without interleaf.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Engineering and Physical Science Research Council (EPSRC) for funding this project. The authors would also like to thank Mr Hugo de Luca for assisting in manufacturing the PES films, Mr Joseph Meggyesi for the mechanical testing and Mr Jonathan Cole for the microscope study.

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